

Design Optimization of Lyocell Fabric Dyeing Parameter by Vat Dye

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Abstract: Successful dyeing of lyocell, a biodegradable regenerated cellulose fiber, in fabric form is still a challenging job. Here in, we report successful dyeing of lyocell fabric with vat dyes by conventional batch wise method. To assess the dye ability of lyocell fabric, a woven lyocell fabric was dyed with Blue colorants of vat dyes by using previously determined procedure for vat dyeing on cellulose fabric. Dyeing parameters (temperature and time) were regulated to attain optimal dyeing conditions. Color yield of dyed lyocell fabric was analyzed using Kubelka –Munk equation, and durability of dyed fabric was examined by standard color fastness properties. Lyocell fabric dyed with vat dyes displayed excellent color strength and remarkable fastness properties under optimized dyeing conditions.

Keywords: Lyocell cotton fabric, Changeable shade% (Vat dye), Variable temperature, Variable time, K/S value, Sigle factor, L9 Design, Optimum results.

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Accepted: 15 April, 2024; **Published:** 15 May, 2024

How to cite this article: Howto cite this article: Md. Iusuf Khan, Masrur Ush Shaheed, Luluel Maknoon ,Ayon Barua, Shetu nath , Khadiza Parvin sumi, Kamrul Hasan, (2024). Design Optimization of Lyocell Fabric Dyeing Parameter by Vat Dye. North American Academic Research, 7(4), 249-265. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11221383>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Lyocell is a semi-synthetic fabric that is commonly used as a substitute for cotton or silk. This fabric is a form of rayon, and it is composed primarily of cellulose derived from wood. Originally developed by American Enka in 1972, lyocell burst into popularity in the latter decades of the 20th century, and it is still relatively popular around the world. Since it is primarily made from organic ingredients, this fabric is seen as a more sustainable alternative to fully synthetic fibers like polyester, but whether or not lyocell fabric is truly better for the environment is questionable. At American Enka, lyocell fabric only made it through the pilot phase of development before the project was abandoned. It wasn't until the 1980s that a British company called Courtaulds Fibres picked up the pieces and created a new fabric called Tencel based on lyocell research. These two fabrics are chemically identical, and the terms Tencel and lyocell can be used interchangeably [1].

Consumers generally find lyocell fabric to be soft to the touch, and many people can't tell the difference between this fabric and cotton. Lyocell fabric is very strong whether it is wet or dry, and it is more resistant to pilling than cotton [2]. Textile manufacturers like the fact that it's easy to mix this fabric with other types of textiles; for instance, it plays well with cotton, silk, rayon, polyester, nylon, and wool.

Made of lyocell fabric

Tencel is almost chemically identical to rayon, but a somewhat different process is used to make this rayon derivative [3]. Unlike the rayon production process, the lyocell fabric production process involves the use of a direct solvent instead of an indirect solvent. A solvent spinning technique is used to create Tencel, which means that unlike the case in the production of rayon, the Tencel production process doesn't cause any significant chemical changes to the chemical structure of cellulose [4]. While fabrics derived from cellulose have been around for nearly 200 years, they have only been in mass production since the beginning of the 20th century. These fabrics were originally designed as substitutes for silk, and pioneers of cellulose fabrics attempted to recreate the process that silkworms use to make real silk [5].

First cellulose fabric to be mass-produced was rayon, and to this day, rayon is made with an extrusion method. As one of the newest cellulose fabric production methods, production of lyocell improves on the production methods used to make rayon [6]. It is more efficient, it produces less waste, and it results in a product that is less synthetic than rayon.

Production Process

Chips of hardwood like oak or birch are used as the raw materials for the cellulose that is used in this fabric. The trees used for these purposes are usually grown on managed tree farms. Once the trees arrive at a Tencel production facility, they are broken down into chips and loaded into a vat of chemical digesters, which soften the chips into pulp [7]. This pulp is then washed in water, and bleach may also be used to sanitize it. Next, it is dried in a sheet, and it is rolled into spools. Most cellulose rolls are enormous and weigh about 500 pounds. These sheets are then broken into squares measuring approximately one inch across, and these squares are placed in pressurized and heated vats of amine oxide, which is the primary solvent used to make lyocell fabric [8]. Once the cellulose has dissolved into a clear liquid, it is filtered and pumped through spinnerets.

As it is forced through spinnerets, cellulose is turned into long, thin fibers. The resulting fibers are immersed in a vat of diluted amine oxide to set, and they are then washed with demineralized water [9]. The lyocell fibers are then dried, and a lubricant, such as silicone or soap, is applied. The fibers are now considered to be in a state called tow, and these bundles of tow are placed in a crimper that compresses the fiber. Next, they are carded, which separates and orders the strands. Lastly, the fibers are cut, and they are then ready to be turned into a variety of different products. Compared to rayon, the Tencel production process requires far fewer steps and takes much less time. Also, since the amine oxide used to make this fabric can be recovered, making lyocell fabric is much less wasteful than making rayon [10].

Used of lyocell fabric

Tencel is usually used as a substitute for cotton or silk. This fabric feels like soft cotton, and it is used to make everything from dress shirts to towels to underwear [10]. While some garments are made entirely from lyocell, it is more common to see this fabric mixed with other types of fabrics like cotton or polyester. Since Tencel is so strong, when it is mixed with other fabrics, the resulting composite fabric is stronger than cotton or polyester on its own. In addition to garments, this fabric is used in a variety of commercial settings. For instance, many manufacturers have substituted lyocell for cotton in the fabric parts of conveyor belts; when belts are made with this fabric, they last longer, and they are more resistant to wear and tear. Furthermore, Tencel is quickly becoming a favorite fabric for medical dressings. In life or death situations, having a fabric that is highly tensile is very important, and Tencel has proved itself to be stronger than fabrics that were used for medical dressings in the past. This fabric's high absorbency profile also makes it an ideal

material to use in medical applications. Soon after its development, scientific researchers recognized the potential of lyocell as a component in specialty papers. While you wouldn't want to write on Tencel paper, many different types of filters are made primarily from paper, and since this fabric has low air resistance and high opacity, it is an ideal filtration material. Since lyocell fabric is such a versatile substance, it may also be used in a variety of specialty applications. Research into this fabric is ongoing, which means that more uses for Tencel may be discovered in the future [11]. Produced of lyocell fabric:

When lyocell fabric was first created, it was only produced at the American Enka factory in Enka, North Carolina. When Enka stopped producing this substance, however, production moved entirely to the United Kingdom when Courtaulds Fibers branded this fabric as Tencel [12].

Tencel production expanded to the Courtaulds plant in Mobile, Alabama, and until the late 1990s, this fabric was not made anywhere else in the world. In 1998, however, Courtaulds was sold to Akzo Nobel, which is a Dutch international corporation specializing in paints. Akzo Nobel went on to sell the rights to Tencel to a private equity firm named CVC partners, which promptly sold its Tencel division to Lenzing AG, which is an international textile corporation based in Austria. [13] While Lenzing AG has a variety of different factories in Europe, a great deal of their production has moved overseas to countries like China and Indonesia. While some Tencel is still produced in countries like Austria, the United Kingdom, and the USA, the majority of this fabric is now produced in China.

Since Lenzing now holds the Tencel patent, it remains the largest producer of this textile in the world [14]. A variety of smaller companies may also make this fabric in minuscule quantities, but if you've worn a lyocell garment, chances are it was made by Lenzing AG in one of their Chinese factories. Rayon and other cellulose fabrics were originally produced as cheaper alternatives to silk. While silk production is all-natural and relatively sustainable, it's hard to produce silk in large.

While it's true that cellulose fabrics remain cheaper to produce than silk, the same can't be said for cotton. While prices of cotton and cellulose fabrics fluctuate, cotton has been significantly cheaper to produce in the last decade [15]. If global economic trends remain stable, cotton will remain less expensive than lyocell and similar fabrics from a production. However, the difference in price between cotton and Tencel is nearly negligible, and some manufacturers may prefer the process of producing cellulose fabrics to the process of manufacturing cotton. Lyocell, in particular, is one of the simplest cellulose fabrics to produce, and it generates very little waste [16]. Vat Dyes

The word vat means, 'Vessel'. The dyes take their name from vatting. The vat dyes are naturally coloring matter and kept in wooden vat and make solubilize vat dyes by the process of fermentation so it is called vat dye. They are applied in a special kind of a dye bath in which the dye is reduced to a soluble form by means of a strong reducing agent, such as hydrosulphite. The vat dyes are insoluble and cannot be used directly and require vatting. Among all the dyes, it has the best fastness properties. Vat dyes are among the most expensive dyes used for dyeing cellulosic materials with best overall fastness properties, including washing fastness, light fastness and chlorine fastness. They are preferred for dyeing work wear or uniforms, or where the textiles and apparels are expected to undergo repeated industrial launderings. Dyes are found from natural sources such as from plants, animals and mineral. But the natural color may not have the desired shade or fastness, it was also scarce and costly but natural dyes applied without using any sort of chemical. These are applied directly to the fabric with the help of edible gum and cow urine. No chemical is used in its dyeing process. Whereas some chemicals such copper sulfate and ferrous sulfate are used as catalysts.1,2 The fabric is 100% cotton free from any chemical, making the free from toxins and irritants with people becoming increasing health conscious the world over. Herbal treated such as neem, turmeric, aloe vera, pomegranate, onion cloth has the ability to protect from various skin diseases, provides relief from viral infected disease and mental depression since herb finished

clothes or garments come in prolonged contact with the human body. The medical properties of herb no damage to the human body and protective the various skin infections but the case of synthetic dyes is available and cheap for commercial use.³⁻⁶ It is extremely harmful environment and health as it leaves a tremendous amount of waste and allergic in contact with human body.

Research Methodology

Materials:

- | Fabric type : Lyocell Fabric
- | Composition : 100% Cotton

Equipment: The following m/c are used in Salim & Brothers ltd -

- | Close bath dyeing machine
- | Small dryer machine.
- | Spectrophotometer

Dyes, Chemical & Auxiliaries Name

1. Dyes Name	: Vat Dye(Blue)
2. Variable Shade%	: 4%, 6% 8%
3. Variable Temperature	: 75°C, 85°C, 95°C
4. Variable Time	: 25 min, 35 min, 45 min.
5. Caustic (NaOH)	: 0.35g
6. Hydroze (Na ₂ S ₂ O ₄)	: 0.28g
7. Leveling Agent	: 15 ml
8. Wetting Agent	: 15 ml
9. Sequestering Agent	: 15 ml
10. M:L	: 1:40
Hydrogen Peroxide 35% (H ₂ O ₂)	: 2 gm/l

Experimental Equipment

1. Beaker
2. Pipette
3. Electric Balance
4. Scissor
5. Ph Paper
6. Spoon
7. PH Meter
8. Glass rod

Method: HTHP Dyeing (High temp high pressure)

HTHP sample Dyeing Machine is a High Temperature and High Pressure Dyeing Machine used by textile manufacturer and educational institutes as lab dyeing. It is also called lab dip dyeing machine. This machine is ideally suitable for dyeing of all kind of fabrics, yarn and loose stock up to temperature of 140 Degree Celsius. This machine is a versatile, compact and maintenance free apparatus suitable for both Polyester and cotton sample dyeing. In fact it is suitable for dyeing of any fiber in form. The apparatus is of immense use for dyeing and processing units research/testing labs, textile engineering institutes and dyes manufacturers. This Dyeing Machine is also used in textile dyeing factory to stimulate the actual dyeing production process.

Specifications

- Beaker Volume : 500ml
- Beaker quantity : 12pcs
- Max. dyeing temperature : 135°C
- Heating medium : Glycerol
- Glycerol loading capacity : 35L
- Thermostatic time : 0~99min
- Rotor speed : 40rpm
- Max. program : 9
- Steps for each program : 9
- Minimum liquor ratio : 1:5

Figure: 1 HTHP Sample Dyeing Machine

Dryer Machine

Application: Used in textile finishing or drying. All types of fabric can dry on it.

Specifications:

- Temp range 40°C to 200°C, preset at 163°C
- Supplied with 2 off aluminum turntables
- Stainless steel interior
- Independent overheat thermostat
- High accuracy

- Excellent stability
- Low chamber uniformity
- Options
- Capable to hold 3 racks total.

Design

The exterior is constructed from sheet steel finished in easy clean powder coated paint. The interior chamber is made from 304 stainless steel. The unit is well insulated and has a double glazed window to view the test chamber. Two rotating turntables of 13.5in diameter are supplied to perform both tests Heated by Incoloy sheathed elements positioned in the base of the unit. The control system comprises of a highly accurate PID temperature controller and an independent overheat thermostat with calibrated scale and tamper proof lock. Temperature is controlled and pre-set at 163°C.

Figure: 2 Sample Dryer Machines

Dyeing Procedure

1. Firstly we gathered nine fabrics (Made of 100% Lyocell cotton fabric) sample each of 7 gm and collect from Well Fabrics & Well Composite Knit Limited as well as some chemical and auxiliaries.
2. We took nine dyeing pot and put the dye and vatting chemicals in them and run the sample dyeing machine at 60°C for 20 min.
3. After vatting, we put the fabric & dyeing chemicals in those dyeing pot & run the machine at 85 °C for 35 min.
4. After dyeing, oxidization process is done by Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) the sample at 40 °C for 15 min.
5. Then wash the sample, neutralization and drying.
6. Finally we got the K/S value from Spectrophotometer.

Figure: 3 Dyeing curve

Color strength (K/S)

Reflectance (%) of the dyed fabric samples were measured by using Data color 65 observer spectrophotometer. Strength of any colorant (dyestuff / pigment) is related to absorption property. Kubelka–Munk theory gives us the following relation between reflectance and absorbance, which is given bellow in Equation 1.

$$K/S = [(1-R)^2 / 2R] \text{ -----(2)}$$

Where R is the reflectance, K is absorbance and S is the scattering. By using the above equation color strength of different samples were measured.

Variable Shade%: Single factor experiment design analysis based on variable Shade% which is given below in Table 1.

Table 1: Variable Shade%

Shade%	Temperature (°C)	Time (min)
4%	85	35
6%		
8%		

In this above experimental single factor analysis, we assume the temperature at 85°C and time for 35 minute and

just variable shade from 4% to 8%. After finishing the process we found the suitable variable shade 6% became highest the K/S value.

Variable Temperature (°C): Single factor experiment design analysis based on variable Temperature which is given below in Table 2

Table 2: Variable Temperature

Temperature (°C)	Shade %	Time (min)
75	6%	35
85		
95		

From the table 1 we got suitable shade 6%, assume time for 35 minute and variable temperature from 75°C to 95°C which suitable temperature is 85°C based on highest K/S value.

Variable Time (Min): Single factor experiment design analysis based on Changeable Time which is given below in Table 3

Table 3 Variable Time

Time (min)	Shade%	Temperature (°C)
25	6%	85
35		
45		

From the table 1 & table 2 we got suitable shade 6%, suitable temperature 85°C, and variable time from 25 min to 45 min which suitable time 35 min based on maximum KS value.

Optimum Data Analysis: We got the Optimum results from single factor (based on K/S value) above the data analysis which is given below:

Table 4: Optimum Data Analysis

Shade%	Temperature (°C)	Time (min)
6%	95	35

Finally, from table 4 we got the suitable time for 35 minutes and suitable temperature 95 °C and also suitable shade 6%.

Result & Discussion

Identification of Control Parameters and Levels:

Subsequently, nine groups combination of coded parameters has been performed and the result of the measured reflectance of the predominant wavelength at 640nm was exhibited. The experiments were conducted by following the settings of parameters by using color spectrophotometer to measure the color strength in the dyeing process. Settings of parameters were determined by the orthogonal array L9. Response of this experiment is the color strength that was measured by the reflectance (R) that was adopted from Kubelka-Munk theory which is shown below in equation 2,

$$K S = (1-R)^2 / 2R \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

L9 Taguchi Experimental Design analysis design which is given below in Table 5: L9 Design analysis

Run	X1	X2	X3
1	1	1	1
2	1	2	2
3	1	3	3
4	2	2	1
5	2	3	2
6	2	1	3
7	3	3	1
8	3	1	2
9	3	2	3

Recent industrial applications have been particularly associated with the name of the Japanese engineer, G. Taguchi. The Taguchi method optimizes design parameters to minimize variation before optimizing design to hit mean target values for output parameters. The Taguchi method uses special orthogonal arrays to study all the design factors with minimum of experiments. The Taguchi method is one of the best experimental methodologies used to find the minimum number of experiments to be performed within the permissible limit of factors and levels. The comparative study was performed for volumetric wear of Nano hydroxyapatite and MTA-filled dental composites using a combination of four factors, each having five levels. The S/N ratio for the smaller is better characteristic was to find the best condition for the minimum volumetric wear rate.

Table 6: Taguchi Experimental Design analysis

Shade (%)	Time (min)	Temp (°C)	K/S Value	SNRA1	MEAN1
4	25	75	1.42	3.04577	1.42
4	35	85	1.46	3.28706	1.46
4	45	95	1.45	3.22736	1.45
6	25	85	1.47	3.34635	1.47
6	35	95	1.50	3.52183	1.50
6	45	75	1.48	3.40523	1.48
8	25	95	1.44	3.16725	1.44
8	35	75	1.46	3.28706	1.46
8	45	85	1.47	3.34635	1.47

Taguchi Design Summary

Taguchi Array	L9(3 ³)
Factors:	3
Runs:	9

Taguchi Analysis:

Taguchi used the signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio to measure the value of the quality characteristics of the choice. S/N is characterized into three categories: Nominal is the better, smaller the better and larger the better. In this paper, the larger the better character was applied with due to the intention to achieve higher dyeing rate on the cotton knit fabric which is shown below in table 7 and 8.

Response Table for Signal to Noise Ratios Larger is better

Level	Shade (%)	Time (min)	Temperature (°C)
1	3.187	3.186	3.285
2	3.227	3.345	3.287
3	3.424	3.307	3.267
Delta	0.238	0.159	0.019
Rank	1	2	3

Response Table for Signal to Noise Ratios Larger is better

Level	Shade (%)	Time (min)	Temperature (°C)
1	3.187	3.186	3.246
2	3.424	3.365	3.327
3	3.267	3.326	3.305
Delta	0.238	0.179	0.081
Rank	1	2	3

The highest plots of each parameter were chosen as could be seen in table 8, with the reason that the ratio set was the larger the better. The same optimum conditions could be seen by the delta values therefore, the optimum conditions obtained by this approach are as follows: shade time and temperature.

Figure: 4 Signal to noise ratio

As mentioned before, the character of S/N Ratio used in this paper is the larger the better. Therefore, the greater the delta value of a parameter is the better. The optimum conditions on this approach obtained by sorting the delta in an order of significantly affecting the process. The higher the delta value signifies the more effect its parameter contributes which is shown below in figure 5 Effects plot for mean.

Figure: 5 Effects plot for mean

Best Results

Shade %	6
Dyeing time (min)	35
Dyeing temperature (°C)	85

Anova Table: Regression Analysis: K/S Value versus Shade (%), Time (min), Temp (°C)

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Seq SS	Contribution	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Regression	3	0.002558	44.03%	0.002558	0.000853	1.57	0.291
Shade (%)	1	0.000859	14.79%	0.000484	0.000484	0.89	0.381
Time (min)	1	0.001386	23.86%	0.001221	0.001221	2.25	0.184
Temp (°C)	1	0.000313	5.39%	0.000313	0.000313	0.58	0.476
Error	6	0.003252	55.97%	0.003252	0.000542		
Lack-of-Fit	5	0.003252	55.97%	0.003252	0.000650	*	*
Pure Error	1	0.000000	0.00%	0.000000	0.000000		
Total	9	0.005810	100.00%				

Regression Equation

$$K/S \text{ Value} = 1.3290 + 0.00425 \text{ Shade (\%)} + 0.001351 \text{ Time (min)} + 0.000684 \text{ Temp (°C)}$$

One-way ANOVA: K/S Value versus Shade (%)

Method

Null hypothesis	All means are equal
Alternative hypothesis	Not all means are equal
Significance level	$\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor	Levels	Values
Shade (%)	3	4, 6, 8

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Shade (%)	2	0.003602	0.001801	5.71	0.034
Error	7	0.002208	0.000315		
Total	9	0.005810			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0177616	61.99%	51.13%	24.84%

Means

Shade				
(%)	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
4	4	1.4375	0.0206	(1.4165, 1.4585)
6	3	1.48333	0.01528	(1.45908, 1.50758)
8	3	1.45667	0.01528	(1.43242, 1.48092)

Pooled StDev = 0.0177616

Shade (%)	Time (min)	Temp (°C)	K/S Value	RESI (Shade)	RESI_1 (Temp)	RESI_2 (Time)
4	25	75	1.42	-0.0175000	-0.0250000	-0.0175000
4	35	85	1.46	0.0225000	-0.0066667	-0.0133333
4	45	95	1.45	0.0125000	-0.0133333	-0.0166667
6	25	85	1.47	-0.0133333	0.0033333	0.0325000
6	35	95	1.50	0.0166667	0.0366667	0.0266667
6	45	75	1.48	-0.0033333	0.0350000	0.0133333
8	25	95	1.44	-0.0166667	-0.0233333	0.0025000
8	35	75	1.46	0.0033333	0.0150000	-0.0133333
8	45	85	1.47	0.0133333	0.0033333	0.0033333

One-way ANOVA: K/S Value versus Temp (°C)

Method

Null hypothesis	All means are equal
Alternative hypothesis	Not all means are equal
Significance level	$\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor	Levels	Values
Temp (°C)	3	75, 85, 95

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Temp (°C)	2	0.000977	0.000488	0.71	0.525
Error	7	0.004833	0.000690		
Total	9	0.005810			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0262769	16.81%	0.00%	0.00%

Means

Temp (°C)	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
75	4	1.4450	0.0300	(1.4139, 1.4761)
85	3	1.46667	0.00577	(1.43079, 1.50254)
95	3	1.4633	0.0321	(1.4275, 1.4992)

Pooled StDev = 0.0262769

Method

Null hypothesis	All means are equal
Alternative hypothesis	Not all means are equal
Significance level	$\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor	Levels	Values
Time (min)	3	25, 35, 45

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Time (min)	2	0.002602	0.001301	2.84	0.125
Error	7	0.003208	0.000458		
Total	9	0.005810			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0214087	44.78%	29.00%	0.00%

Means

Time (min)		N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
25	4	4	1.4375	0.0236	(1.4122, 1.4628)
35	3	3	1.4733	0.0231	(1.4441, 1.5026)
45	3	3	1.4667	0.01528	(1.43744, 1.49589)

Pooled StDev = 0.0214087

Conclusion

In summary, we successfully devised a strategy for successful uniform dyeing of Lyocell fabric using vat dyes through high temperature dyeing technique. By using Taguchi method and ANOVA we obtained the same result of optimum conditions. The following are the parameters (and levels) in order of significantly affecting the dye process. Dye Concentration (6%), Time 35 (min), Temperature 85 °C. The predicted result compared to the experiments is verified. Therefore, the obtained optimum conditions are proven to be effective. The optimization process that performed by Taguchi method brings out the best conditions to be used in a dyeing process that could actualize a friendly environmental process in a textile industry.

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